

Predictive Channel State Information (CSI) Framework: Evolutional CSI Neural Network (evoCSINet)

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Abstract—In this paper, we present evoCSINet, a predictive channel state information (CSI) framework that learns latent dynamics of radio channel for prediction applications. The framework uses deep neural networks to identify the dynamics representations from radio channel images. The latent dynamics has the potential to enable a recursive multi-step-ahead prediction in latent space. The proposed evoCSINet framework, in turn, provides an accurate multi-step-ahead prediction model under 3GPP CSI feedback mechanism. We demonstrate the effectiveness of the evoCSINet-based CSI prediction through evaluations of channel predictions and investigate its impact on the performance of feedback-based precoding scheme in multi-antenna systems. Our experimental results show that the proposed evoCSINet can guarantee a minimum percentage capacity of 95% of the upper capacity bound, at a UE speed 15km/h, up to a prediction depth of 10 slots ahead.

Index Terms—Radio channel, Temporal evolution dynamics, Channel prediction, Predictive channel state information (CSI) framework

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, many artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms have been used to solve challenging network optimization problems in general and physical layer problems in particular [1]. A new study item on AI for the air interface has been approved by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) to define 5G advanced systems in Release 18, with focus on the three use cases of channel state information (CSI) feedback enhancement, beam management and positioning [2]. In this paper, we address the channel prediction problem as an important building block for 5G-Advanced and 6G

In time division duplexing (TDD) systems, downlink CSI can be obtained from uplink channel observations due to channel reciprocity. For example, in new radio (NR) specifications, user equipment (UE) transmits periodic sounding reference signals (SRSs), allowing the base station (BS) to estimate the downlink channel state. TDD enables assuming full CSI at the BS, which is used for precoding design in downlink multi-antenna systems. Advanced ML methods for channel estimation and prediction have been proposed in [3], [4] and [5]. However, in frequency division duplexing

(FDD) systems where channel reciprocity is not available, the downlink CSI is estimated at the UE and the estimated CSI is sent to the BS through a feedback report in uplink. In FDD systems, the CSI feedback incurs high overhead, motivating the study of ML-based CSI feedback enhancements in 3GPP [2]. An *autoencoder* (AE) can be used for dimensionality reduction and minimize feedback overhead, improving feedback accuracy at a maintained overhead compared to the conventional CSI feedback techniques [6]. The AE-based CSI compression has been the most popular implementation for the ML-based CSI feedback enhancement in the Release-18 study [2] [7]. Unfortunately, AE-based CSI compression may suffer performance degradation due to channel aging in a dynamic network since the AE model cannot capture the time-varying nature of the wireless channel. To avoid the channel aging issues, in this paper we aim at developing a deep learning-based solution that allows the BS to accurately predict radio channel variations under the 3GPP CSI feedback mechanism.

Radio channel describes the relation between the transmitted and received signals [8]. An accurate channel prediction requires a model for the temporal channel evolution. Consider a discrete-time dynamical system, in a state (or observation) space, given by

$$\mathbf{H}_{k+1} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{H}_k), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{H}_k is the state of radio channel at the k -th time step and \mathbf{f} represents a *dynamics* that maps the state \mathbf{H}_k one step forward in discrete time. The temporal evolution dynamics of radio channel is generally nonlinear and the true dynamics is typically unknown due to the underlying complex propagation phenomenon that can not be captured by using the domain knowledge.

In general, predicting a sequence of states in multi-step-ahead problems is more challenging than predicting a single next state in single-step-ahead predictions. Aiming at multi-step-ahead prediction based on a single feedback information under the CSI feedback process, in this paper we propose an evolutional CSI Neural Network (evoCSINet), a CSI framework that learns latent dynamics of radio channel for predic-

tion applications. The proposed evoCSINet uses deep neural networks, which have proven to be very efficient for a broad range of computer vision problems [9], as a parameterized function approximator to identify the unknown true channel dynamics in (1) from data. We introduce a *dynamicNet* that can learn the temporal evolution of radio channel in latent space. This model has the potential to enable a recursive multi-step prediction in the latent space. The proposed evoCSINet applies the combination of autoencoder and dynamicNet to identify latent-level representation of channel dynamics from radio channel images given by channel states \mathbf{H}_k . Through learning the latent dynamics representation, we can optimize our evoCSINet towards multi-step predictions. The proposed evoCSINet provides a factorized representation of radio channel dynamics that allows evoCSINet to fit into the 3GPP CSI feedback procedure. As a result, the evoCSINet can achieve an accurate multi-step-ahead prediction only based on the single feedback information of an encoded vector, called latent code.

We demonstrate the effectiveness of the evoCSINet-based CSI prediction through evaluations of channel predictions under the 3GPP CSI feedback mechanism and investigate its impact on the performance of feedback-based precoding scheme in multi-antenna systems. To quantify impact of channel aging and prediction under the CSI feedback procedure, we evaluate the performance degradation due to outdated CSI compared to perfect CSI and the performance improvement thanks to predicted CSI. This paper uses synthetic data generated by using 3GPP 5G channel models [10]. Our simulations show that the proposed evoCSINet can guarantee at least 95% of the upper capacity bound, at a UE speed 15km/h, up to a prediction depth of 10 time slots ahead.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we present a novel evoCSINet framework. Section III describes implementation of the proposed evoCSINet under the 3GPP CSI feedback mechanism and address specification impacts. In Section IV, we present performance comparisons with the AE-based CSI compression. Finally, conclusions are made in Section V.

II. PREDICTIVE CSI FRAMEWORK: EVOCSINET

In this section, we present the proposed evoCSINet and describe the basic idea of evoCSINet-based CSI prediction, compared to AE-based CSI compression.

In FDD systems, channel state can be observed through channel estimations by UE. In particular, in slot-based NR systems, the channel state \mathbf{H}_k at a slot time k can be represented by the channel response matrices of size equal to $T \times N$, where T and N are, respectively, the numbers of orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) symbols and subcarriers estimated within a slot. In this work, channel states are given by real- or imaginary-part of the temporal-frequency channel matrices, i.e., $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times N}$. Each channel matrix \mathbf{H}_k can be represented by a two-dimensional image and hence each channel image provides dynamical contextual information about the underlying channel of wireless communication system. We formulate channel prediction problem as

Fig. 1. Schematic diagrams of two deep learning models: (a) CSI compression by Autoencoder (b) CSI prediction by proposed evolutionary CSI neural network (evoCSINet)

image prediction problem in the temporal-frequency domain. Specifically, given a channel image of state $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times N}$, we predict a sequence of images that represents the sequence of future channel states.

A. Autoencoder (AE) for CSI compression

We first provide a brief description of the CSI compression based on autoencoder. The aim of AE-based CSI compression is to minimize signal overhead or reconstruction error through dimensionality reduction [2] [7].

Figure 1a illustrates the AE-based CSI feedback enhancement based on autoencoder with encoder ϕ and decoder ϕ^{-1} . The encoder part of autoencoder is located on the UE side to compress channel data into a reduced dimensional space while its decoder part is applied on the BS side to reconstruct the original channel data from the compressed feedback. Therefore, the objective of AE-based CSI compression is to satisfy the following condition

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \phi^{-1}(\phi(\mathbf{H}_k)). \quad (2)$$

Dimension reduction occurs when high-dimensional states \mathbf{H}_k are encoded to a low dimensional approximation, latent code $\mathbf{z}_k = \phi(\mathbf{H}_k)$, which enables us to minimize the feedback overhead imposed by \mathbf{z}_k . Unfortunately, the CSI available at the BS becomes outdated due to the channel variation over time and the performance of precoding design based on the outdated CSI is limited by channel aging. Moreover, it is not possible to predict the temporal evolution of radio channel under the AE-based CSI feedback schemes currently being considered within Release-18.

B. evolutionary CSI Neural Network (evoCSINet) for CSI prediction

As we aim at achieving multi-step-ahead predictions based on the single feedback information, we introduce a dynamicNet \mathcal{F} that learns the temporal evolution of radio channel in a latent space. In particular, the latent dynamic model identifies a low-dimensional representation of channel dynamics from channel data to predict a latent code one step forward in time as follows:

$$\mathbf{z}_{k+\Delta} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{z}_k), \quad (3)$$

where Δ denotes a configurable stride in slot time and \mathcal{F} represents the same dynamical system as \mathbf{f} in (1) but in a different space.

A diagram of the proposed evoCSINet is shown in Figure 1b. The evoCSINet applies the combination of autoencoder with dynamicNet. In the proposed evoCSINet model, an autoencoder, composed of ϕ and ϕ^{-1} , achieves an end-to-end CSI compression and reconstruction by learning the state representation in the original channel state space. The two ingredients of autoencoder in (2) and dynamicNet in (3) enable a dynamics representation of radio channel (1) as

$$\mathbf{H}_{k+\Delta} = \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}(\phi(\mathbf{H}_k))), \quad (4)$$

where dynamicNet \mathcal{F} uses the encoder output $\phi(\mathbf{H}_k)$ as an input to produce its output $\phi(\mathbf{H}_{k+\Delta})$ and it is processed by the decoder to produce $\mathbf{H}_{k+\Delta}$.

The factorized decomposition of channel dynamics in (4) is especially advantageous for our problem setting since the decomposition of ϕ and ϕ^{-1} along with \mathcal{F} in a latent space allows evoCSINet to fit into the CSI feedback procedure.

More importantly, as shown in Figure 1b, a multi-step channel prediction can be achieved in latent space by applying the dynamicNet \mathcal{F} in a recursive manner, leading to

$$\mathbf{H}_{k+m\Delta} = \phi^{-1}\left(\mathcal{F}^{(m)}(\phi(\mathbf{H}_k))\right), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{F}^{(m)}(\cdot)$ indicates a m -time recursive process of \mathcal{F} to the latent code $\phi(\mathbf{H}_k)$. A recursive multi-step-ahead prediction in the latent space can be generated with \mathcal{F} by predicting a channel state at a time step and feeding in the new prediction as an input for the next prediction.

Deep learning is applied on channel data to approximate the three parts ϕ , \mathcal{F} , and ϕ^{-1} of the target evoCSINet model by three neural networks, denoted by ϕ_θ , \mathcal{F}_θ , and ϕ_θ^{-1} , respectively. In order to maximize prediction accuracy over D future time steps, we define a loss function with an objective to achieve a balance between state-level reconstruction and latent-level prediction errors, which leads to a trade-off between immediate predictions and long-term predictions.

The loss function consists of three loss terms; a reconstruction loss l_ϕ and a multi-step prediction loss $l_{\phi,\mathcal{F}}$ in state-level loss, and a multi-step prediction loss $l_{\mathcal{F}}$ in latent-level loss. The reconstruction loss term l_ϕ is defined between reconstruction output $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k = \phi_\theta^{-1}(\phi_\theta(\mathbf{H}_k))$ and target state \mathbf{H}_k , with the encoder ϕ and decoder ϕ^{-1} only, as follows:

$$l_\phi = \|\mathbf{H}_k - \phi_\theta^{-1}(\phi_\theta(\mathbf{H}_k))\|, \quad (6)$$

where the norm $\|\cdot\|$ is defined by mean absolute error (MAE), also known as L_1 loss function, on all the pixels between matrices or vectors.

We define the two multi-step prediction loss terms $l_{\phi,\mathcal{F}}$ and $l_{\mathcal{F}}$ as

$$l_{\phi,\mathcal{F}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \left\| \mathbf{H}_{k+m\Delta} - \phi_\theta^{-1}\left(\mathcal{F}_\theta^{(m)}(\phi_\theta(\mathbf{H}_k))\right) \right\|, \quad (7)$$

and

$$l_{\mathcal{F}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \left\| \phi_\theta(\mathbf{H}_{k+m\Delta}) - \mathcal{F}_\theta^{(m)}(\phi_\theta(\mathbf{H}_k)) \right\|, \quad (8)$$

where a hyperparameter M is the number of steps to be iteratively predicted by \mathcal{F} in a latent space in the training phase.

To update the three neural networks ϕ_θ , \mathcal{F}_θ , and ϕ_θ^{-1} in training process, we use the following weighted loss function of three loss terms

$$l_{evo} = l_{\phi,\mathcal{F}} + \alpha l_\phi + \beta l_{\mathcal{F}}, \quad (9)$$

where the hyperparameters α and β are used to achieve a compromise between the three loss terms by defining importance of terms l_ϕ and $l_{\mathcal{F}}$, relative to the main loss term $l_{\phi,\mathcal{F}}$.

We will build our evoCSINet by using the architecture proposed in [9] that have been shown to be very effective in many image processing tasks involving high-dimensional data. The encoder and decoder consist of seven convolution and transposed convolution layers, respectively, and each of them is designed with about 0.83 million parameters. The convolutional layers in the encoder use LeakyReLU as an activation function while the transposed convolutional layers in the decoder use ReLU except the last layer that uses tanh. All the layers in the encoder and decoder are followed by batch normalization prior to the activation function except the input layer of encoder and the output layer of decoder. Dropout layers are added for the first two layers of the decoder in order to prevent overfitting of the model. The same encoder and decoder architectures are used for both AE-based CSI compression and evoCSINet-based CSI prediction. A shallow dynamicNet is built with a single, fully connected layer with the same size as the latent code size, that uses ReLU as the activation function. Compression rate is given by the ratio of latent code size to the original channel state size. All the model trainings have been performed under the same compression rate of $\frac{1}{8}$, i.e., the size of latent code \mathbf{z}_k is set to be 64. The three component networks ϕ_θ , \mathcal{F}_θ , and ϕ_θ^{-1} are trained by performing gradient descent on the loss function in (9).

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND SPECIFICATION

In this section, we describe how evoCSINet can be incorporated to the CSI feedback procedure in BS-centric manner and address specification impacts.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of feedback-based precoding design based on the proposed evoCSINet, assuming the stride $\Delta = 2$

A. BS-centric prediction with evoCSINet

The factorized decomposition of the proposed evoCSINet given in (5) allows two different implementations, namely, BS-centric and UE-centric predictions. In this work, we consider a BS-centric prediction with the prediction depth D , where the BS acquires the encoded CSI of downlink channel state \mathbf{H}_k at a slot k and wishes to accurately forecast the next D channel states $\mathbf{H}_{k+1}, \mathbf{H}_{k+2}, \dots, \mathbf{H}_{k+D}$ into the future.

Figure 2 depicts a schematic diagram of a BS-centric CSI prediction with the proposed evoCSINet, where the evoCSINet is split into UE and BS sides: encoder ϕ at the UE side, and dynamicNet \mathcal{F} and decoder ϕ^{-1} at the BS side. Note that the single CSI feedback $\mathbf{z}_k = \phi(\mathbf{H}_k)$ from the slot k is used for precoding-based data transmission over the following slots, until the next CSI update. Therefore, the prediction depth D is determined by the CSI feedback periodicity, which is specified in the 3GPP standards. Throughout this paper, we assume the CSI periodicity to be 10 slots, corresponding to the baseline time periodicity of 5ms being considered in the Release-18 study item on AI for the air interface. This means that the BS should forecast the variation of CSI from \mathbf{H}_{k+1} to \mathbf{H}_{k+9} with the prediction depth $D = 9$ based on the single CSI feedback \mathbf{z}_k .

As can be seen in Figure 1, the proposed evoCSINet is able to predict an infinite number of time points $k + m\Delta$ for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, with a stride Δ over an infinite time horizon, all measured in slot time. The remaining time points will be obtained through a simple procedure including rounding to the nearest neighbour points and linear interpolation between two neighbour points. For an illustrative example, Figure 2 contains a channel interpolation and precoding design block that performs linear interpolation to obtain precoding vectors for each slot based on the directly predicted CSIs on the time grid given by $\Delta = 2$.

B. Specification impacts

To support the proposed CSI prediction solution in 3GPP specifications and accommodate different BS-centric imple-

Fig. 3. New RS pattern, defined on a PRB basis, for supporting the proposed CSI prediction approach

mentations, a new mechanism for related signalling is required, for example, to inform UE about implementation option along with a reference signal (RS) for channel state estimation and prediction stride Δ for latent code generation. The RS for state estimation can be either of the existing CSI-RS (CSI-RS) or a new CSI-RS configuration, and a new quasi-colocation (QCL) type can also be defined with a source RS to assist UE in generating a latent code.

Figure 3 shows an exemplary new CSI-RS configuration that can be used for state estimation in downlink. The CSI-RS configurations are defined on a physical resource block (PRB) basis, where one PRB consists of 14 OFDM symbols in time domain and spans 12 subcarriers in frequency domain in NR systems. A resource element (RE) is the smallest physical resource, defined by one subcarrier during one OFDM symbol. In Figure 3, the red squares indicate the REs used for estimating the state \mathbf{H}_k at the CSI update slot k , while the blue squares represent the REs to be predicted in forecasting future states \mathbf{H}_{k+m} at the slot $k + m$.

We can specify that the prediction strides of Δ shall be associated with UE mobility and/or channel condition between BS and UE. For instance, a set of candidate prediction strides can be predefined in the specification, from which the BS selects the best one and signals it to the UE dynamically via downlink control information (DCI) or semi-statically via radio resource control (RRC) configuration. It is expected that the UE generates latent codes by assuming the values of Δ configured by the BS.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATIONS

In this section, we present performance comparisons with the AE-based CSI compression to demonstrate the effectiveness of the evoCSINet-based CSI prediction.

In this work, we designed evoCSINet to forecast channel states in the temporal-frequency domain in a single-input single-output (SISO) OFDM system. For the sake of performance evaluation, the prediction accuracy is quantified using outage capacity as channel capacity degrades with aged CSI in

multi-antenna systems. We consider the outage capacity of a rank-1 precoding scheme over the 8-by-1 multiple input single output (MISO) spatial channel. The same evoCSINet model is used for CSI predictions between each pair of transmit and receive antennas in a MISO system.

The ϵ -outage capacity is defined as maximum rate below which reliable transmission is possible at outage probability of ϵ (p_{out}) [11]

$$C_\epsilon = \max_r \left\{ p_{out} \left[\log_2 \left(1 + \rho |\mathbf{c}_{(t,f)} \mathbf{w}_{(t,f)}|^2 \right) \leq r \right] \leq \epsilon \right\} \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) parameter, $\mathbf{c}_{(t,f)} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times n_t}$ denotes the complex-valued channel vectors at the (t, f) th element of ground truth, and $\mathbf{w}_{(t,f)} \in \mathbb{C}^{n_t \times 1}$ represents the precoding vector obtained by outdated or predicted CSI at the (t, f) th element, with $n_t = 8$ in the 8-by-1 MISO.

The maximum ratio transmission (MRT) precoding is optimal for this MISO setup by maximizing the signal gain, and CSI at the transmitter is required to enable the precoding. We will compare the three different CSI assumptions including perfect CSI, compressed CSI based on AE-based CSI compression, and predicted CSI based on the proposed evoCSINet-based CSI prediction, represented by an unit-norm vector $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{tr}$, $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{cmp}$, and $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{pr}$, respectively. The MRT solution is given by $\mathbf{w}_{(t,f)}^{mrt} = \hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^\dagger$, where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the conjugate transpose of vector and $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)} \in \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{tr}, \hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{cmp}, \hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{pr} \right\}$. We evaluate 10% outage capacity performance ($\epsilon=0.1$) under the three different CSI assumptions; perfect CSI $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{tr}$, compressed CSI $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{cmp}$, and predicted CSI $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_{(t,f)}^{pr}$, and normalize it by the upper capacity bound with the perfect CSI in order to quantify prediction performance loss relative to the upper bound.

Let us briefly describe the impact of hyperparameters M , α , and β . As can be seen in Figure 2, in the inference phase the proposed evoCSINet is able to forecast channel states on a grid of time points $k + m\Delta$ for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, over an infinite time horizon. On the other hand, in this work the evoCSINet is used for the application to precoding design and we aim to maximize the value of minimum prediction accuracy in the limited time horizon given by prediction window. To this end, we can optimize *prediction time grid* that specifies the time points to be used in the loss terms (7) and (8) in the training phase. A prediction time grid of evoCSINet consists of $M + 1$ time points $k + m\Delta$ for $m = 0, 1, \dots, M$, that can be adaptively determined by the hyperparameter M as well as Δ . For the discussion in this paper, predictions near the beginning of the prediction window are referred to as immediate predictions while predictions close to the end of the prediction window are described as long-term predictions. The hyperparameters α and β can be adjusted to achieve the best trade-off between immediate predictions and long-term predictions. For instance, from the definitions of the loss terms in (7) and (6), the loss term l_ϕ is related to the performance at the initial prediction point k while the loss term $l_{\phi, \mathcal{F}}$ is related to the performance at the rest of prediction points $k + m\Delta$ for $m = 1, \dots, M$. Therefore,

TABLE I
CHANNEL MODEL PARAMETERS FOR DATA GENERATION

Parameter	Value
Duplex	FDD
Channel model	5G channel model according to [10]
Scenario	Urban Macro
Frequency	4.9GHz
Inter-BS distance	200m
Numerology (slot/subcarrier spacing (SCS))	14 OFDM symbols per slot, SCS 30kHz
CSI feedback periodicity	10 slots, i.e., 5ms (no scheduling delay)
UE distribution	100% outdoor/NLOS, 15km/h
Ports	8 ports at BS, 1 port at UE
Evaluation metric	10%-outage capacity at SNR 30dB

increasing α leads to performance improvements in the long-term prediction accuracy at a cost of degradation in the immediate prediction accuracy. While omitted from this paper due to space constraints, we have undertaken simulations to determine the optimal hyperparameters: $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 10^{-2}$ for a prediction depth of $D = 9$. The same values will be used in our simulation work to train the models ϕ_θ , \mathcal{F}_θ , and ϕ_θ^{-1} .

For performance simulations and analysis of its impact on precoding performance, we generated channel realizations using 3GPP 5G channel models [10]. The data set are created with 15000 state sequences with length 12. The main system parameters used are listed in Table I. Urban macro (UMa) model is specified as simulation environment. We assume carrier frequency 4.9 GHz. A slot is defined as 14 OFDM symbols and the length of one slot is 0.5 ms with 30kHz subcarrier spacing. Throughout this work, the new CSI-RS configuration illustrated in Figure 3 with a comb-factor 6 in frequency domain, i.e., every 6th subcarrier, is used for performance evaluation and the number of available PRBs is assumed to be 64, i.e., $N = 64 \cdot 2$. Then, the corresponding channel states can be represented by the channel matrices of size $T \times N = 4 \times 128$, i.e., $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 128}$. For UE mobility model, all UEs are assumed to be outdoor user at speed 15km/h in non line-of-sight (NLOS) environments. The evaluations are performed over the 8-port BS and 1-port UE antenna setup in FDD downlink channels.

Figure 4 depicts two sequences of channel images; the first one for the true channels and the second one for the predicted channels, where each subfigure corresponds to the sequence of ten channel states $\mathbf{H}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 128}$ from slot k to $k + 9$. The stride $\Delta = 1$ is assumed to predict and visualize the channels at every slot without use of linear interpolation. The results demonstrate that the proposed evoCSINet-based CSI prediction can successfully predict channels up to 9 steps ahead in time.

In Figure 5, we compare the percentage capacity obtained with three different prediction time grids, offering different trade-offs between immediate and long-term predictions in a given limited time horizon. The prediction time grids generate a specific set of time points with the same initial point k , but using different values of strides. The first thing we

Fig. 4. An exemplary channel prediction result : a) sequence of the true channel images and (b) sequence of the predicted channel images

Fig. 5. Impact of stride Δ and hyperparameter M in prediction accuracy within the prediction window of size 9

notice from Figure 5 is that the MRT precoding with the compressed CSI suffers from a severe performance loss due to channel aging. For instance, the performance loss reaches 23% at the CSI aging of 9 slots, compared to the ideal CSI. The second observation from Figure 5 is that performance degradations due to channel aging are marginal over the first few slots, which encourages us to consider stride values Δ greater than one. In order to evaluate the change in accuracy with increasing values of stride Δ , we have simulated for the predicted CSI cases using the three values of $\Delta = 1, 2, 3$. The values of M have been chosen for each time grid to achieve the best balance between immediate and long-term performance within the given prediction window. The plot in Figure 5 shows that the best average performance can be achieved by applying the evoCSINet using $\Delta = 3$ and $M = 3$, meaning that the stride value $\Delta = 3$ does not hurt the performance at the time points off the prediction time grid even though channel states at these points are estimated from the predicted states at its neighbour time points via the simple procedure of rounding and linear interpolation. Note that increasing values

of $\Delta = 1, 2, 3$ resulted in the reduced values of M , which may have contributed to the better performance with $\Delta = 3$ since an evoCSINet model that is trained to predict the smaller numbers of time points will outperform the same evoCSINet trained to predict the larger numbers of time points. The results in Figure 5 demonstrate that the evoCSINet-based CSI prediction can reduce the performance loss due to channel aging by 78%, which corresponds to 95% of the maximum capacity.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a challenging channel prediction problem is viewed as an image prediction problem in the temporal-frequency domain of radio channel. We have proposed evoCSINet, a new CSI framework that utilizes a latent-level dynamics representation of the radio channel to achieve multi-step-ahead prediction based on a single feedback information under 3GPP CSI feedback mechanism. Our framework is parameterized to allow for flexibility in prediction strides and trade-offs between immediate and long-term performance, making it adaptable to different dynamic environments. Capacity analysis reveals the effectiveness of evoCSINet in prediction with high accuracy and the potential of its prediction capability for adaptive precoding design. We anticipate that this new capability will play an important role in the evolution of cellular wireless access towards 5G-Advanced and 6G.

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